

Exploring Students' Perspective in Earth and Life Science Remediation Program: A Phenomenology

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative phenomenological study determined the perspectives of students regarding the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program at Kasiglahan Village Senior High School during the first semester of the academic year 2025–2026. Utilizing purposive sampling, the study selected 15 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students who demonstrated low scores in formative assessments. The remedial sessions utilized contextualized learning activities aligned with essential learning competencies. Data were gathered using a custom questionnaire validated by five master teachers, with parental consent secured, and analyzed through a thematic analysis approach. The findings revealed that students' initial learning difficulties stemmed

from a lack of self-confidence, limited focus, absenteeism, and complex subject terminologies. However, during the remediation program, participants experienced enhanced learning, self-improvement, and improved understanding. This led to a strong perception that the program was highly effective, fostering substantial learning growth, knowledge reinforcement, and heightened self-confidence. Consequently, the students expressed high learning satisfaction with the remedial intervention. To enhance future implementations, participants suggested providing more opportunities for active participation—such as regular recitations and interactive games—to increase student engagement and interest. Additionally, they recommended implementing longer remediation schedules to allow sufficient time for unpacking and understanding complex science lessons. Ultimately, this study serves as a critical basis for refining instructional designs and implementation frameworks for science remediation programs, particularly when addressing the distinct needs of non-STEM students navigating complex scientific concepts.

Keywords: *Earth and Life Science, remediation program, phenomenology, students' perspectives, learning difficulties, qualitative research, thematic analysis, senior high school, academic achievement, instructional intervention*

INTRODUCTION

Earth and Life Science is a core subject in the senior high school program under the K to 12 Curriculum. This subject employ variety of scientific skills which is necessary to real-world applications. However, many students are having difficulty in understanding the subject matter due to different factors such as the subject having complex concepts and terminologies as well as abstract ideas which often lead the students to confusion, reduced class participation, and low academic performance.

To address these challenges, remediation program is commonly practiced providing learning support and interventions to those students that are academically challenged. Remediation may be described as the process of identifying students at risk of failing and implementing strategies to support them.

(Thilges, 2020). Moreover, it is an educational approach which seeks to address the gap between students' current competencies and the skills necessary for success in higher education and the workforce. (Hugh, 2021).

The implementation of the remediation program for the academically challenged students is supported by the curriculum under the Republic Act 10533 or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, which states that the curriculum should be learner-centered and developmentally appropriate, relevant, responsive, and research-based, culture sensitive, contextualized, and global. It gave emphasis in meeting the need of the learners through different approaches such as constructivist, inquiry-based, reflective, collaborative, and integrative.

Throughout the years, despite of the unwavering support of the Department of Education, it is undeniable that there is a great challenge in the Science Education in the Philippines. This is supported by the data of the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) wherein the Philippines ranked 77th out of 81 countries, 76th in Reading Comprehension, 76th in Mathematics and 79th in Science Literacy. Moreover, the Philippines ranked at the bottom of the 64 countries that participated on the said assessment for creative thinking as indicated in the result of PISA 2024. Furthermore, the Department of Education provides an avenue to assess the students' learning through a National Achievement Test. The 2024 National Achievement Test Result revealed that students across all regions and senior high school tracks remain at a Low Proficiency level, highlighting persistent learning deficiencies in key subjects. Across senior high school (SHS) tracks, students struggled the most in science, mathematics, language, and communication, subjects critical for higher education and employment.

With this context, the said curriculum provided the learners the support they need to be able to immerse themselves in the challenging academic conditions of the country. As highlighted by the DepEd Order Number 10 series of 2025, strategic interventions will be implemented to bridge the critical gap between learners' current performance and grade level expectations. These interventions are predicated on the understanding that unmastered learning standards and competencies create significant barriers to future academic success.

This research was conducted to determine the students' difficulties, learning experiences in the Earth and Life Science remediation program as well as their suggestions for the improvement of the design and implementation of the remediation program. This also analyzed their perspective on how the remediation program influenced their learning experiences and outcomes.

Literature Review

The persistent challenges in the sector of education in the Philippines seems to be alarming. This was reported by Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM II) 2026 wherein Filipino learners face a severe literacy crisis, with proficiency dropping from 30.52% in Grade 3 to only 0.47% by Grade 12, leaving only 4 in 1,000 senior high school students proficient. Roughly 85% of early grade learners struggle to read, and approximately 24 million Filipinos are considered functionally illiterate, struggling to apply literacy in daily life. The illiteracy among Filipino learners has an impact in the economy and social welfare. This could greatly affect the economy's future if the illiteracy remains unsolved and the workforce remained unprepared.

Therefore, through remediation program this illiteracy among the Filipino learners could be solved gradually as educators continuously bridge the learning gaps in the academe.

According to Rai and Penjor (2020), remedial class has a positive impact among learners, and this should be implemented in any instruction for more effective outcomes. Moreover, Papadogianis et.al., (2023) stated that remedial teaching is very effective in supporting very weak students it helped students achieve better academic performance.

Furthermore, Burgoños (2025) added that continuous feedback in remedial classes enhances collaboration, focus, self-initiated learning, and task completion. Thus, students struggling in science may

be given personalized learning plans with structured feedback and adaptive instructional methods to enhance their engagement, comprehension, and overall academic success.

Synthesis

The analysis on the students' perspective in the remediation program of Earth and Life Science created an avenue for the exploration of the learners' experiences, emotions, and sense of belongingness which greatly influenced their academic success in remediation program. Their perception of remediation program provided valuable evidence of academic improvement as they personally experience the remediation. Through this, it provided an understanding as to how they experience and value the remediation program and provide meaningful interventions to it.

Research Questions

The general objective of this study is to explore the student's perspective in the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program. This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What difficulties do students encounter in learning Earth and Life Science that led to the need of remediation program?
2. What are the experiences of the students who participated in the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program?
3. How do students perceive the effectiveness of the remediation program?
4. What suggestions do students provide to improve the design and implementation of Earth and Life Science Remediation Program?

Scope and Limitation

The focus of this research was to explore the students' difficulties in learning Earth and Life Science, their perspective and experiences during the Earth and Life Science remediation program, and suggestions for the improvement of the design and implementation of the program. This was conducted in Kasiglahan Village Senior High School, Division of Rizal school year 2025-2026.

The research utilized a qualitative research design which provided questionnaires that were validated by five master teachers in the said school. Respondents of the study were chosen through purposive sampling technique to immediately gather data through the given population for a short period of time and to provide reliable results for the intended remediation program. These are the learners identified with low scores in their formative assessment. The collected data was subjected for thematic analysis approach to identify, analyze, and interpret patterns within the data.

METHODS

The study entitled, "Exploring Students' Perspective in Earth and Life Science Remediation Program: A Phenomenology" utilized a qualitative research design which explore the students' difficulties in learning Earth and Life Science, their perspective and experiences during the Earth and Life Science remediation program, and suggestions for the improvement of design and implementation of the program. This study was conducted in Kasiglahan Village Senior High School, San Jose, Montalban Rizal school year 2025-2026.

To acquire data from the 15 students of HUMSS Strand, which were identified through purposive sampling as students having low scores in formative assessments, these respondents were undergone remediation program for two quarters specifically four weeks for each quarter. Moreover, a questionnaire for the respondents to answer was made which were validated by five master teachers from the same school. The validated questionnaire was administered to the respondents which sought to determine their

difficulties in learning Earth and Life Science, perspective and experiences during the Earth and Life Science remediation program, and suggestions for the improvement of design and implementation of the program.

The data collected were analyzed using thematic analysis approach identifies, organizes, and interprets patterns or themes within the dataset. This approach enabled analysis of data which allowed the researcher to scrutinize key themes that was reflected in the respondents' perspective.

A. Sampling

The sampling technique that was utilized in this study is purposive sampling, non-probability sampling technique where a sample is selected from a population based on the characteristics needed to provide certain data on the given research. Purposive sampling technique was chosen to gather data from the given population which best fit for the study given the timeframe to conduct this research is limited.

B. Data Collection

The researcher utilized a validated questionnaire which prompt an open-ended question for the respondents to answer about their difficulties in learning the subject, experience in the remediation program in Earth and Life Science, their perception on the effectiveness of the remediation program, and their suggestion to further improve the said remediation program. The collected data was subjected for thematic analysis approach to identify, analyze, and interpret patterns within the data.

C. Ethical Issues

The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study signed by the school head in the Kasiglahan Village Senior High School for the legality of the conduct of this research. Moreover, a parent's consent was given to the respondents to participate in the remediation program as well as in the conduct of this research and follow the Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

D. Plan for Data Analysis

The data analysis tool that was utilized in the conduct of this study was thematic analysis approach which determined the respondents' experiences, perspectives, and suggestions in the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program.

Timetable/Gantt Chart

ACTIVITIES	*Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5	Month 6
1. Consolidation of Assessment Scores						
2. Determination of Remediation Program Participant based on Assessment Scores						
3. Conduct of Remediation Program in Earth and Life Science						
4. Development of Questionnaire						
5. Validation of Questionnaire						
6. Administration of the Validated Questionnaire to the Target Participants						
7. Analysis and Interpretation of Data						
8. Development of Conclusion and Recommendation						

**Shade the corresponding month per activity*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. *Themes Generated from Data Analysis*

Research Question	Themes
1. What difficulties do students encounter in learning Earth and Life Science that led to the need of remediation program?	Lack of self-confidence Lack of focus Complex terminologies Absenteeism
2. What are the experiences of the students who participated in the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program?	Enhanced learning Self-improvement Improved understanding
3. How do students perceive the effectiveness of the remediation program?	Improved learning Improved self-confidence Learning growth Knowledge reinforcement
4. What suggestions do students provide to improve the design and implementation of Earth and Life Science Remediation Program?	Learning satisfaction Active participation Interactive activities Remediation schedules

1. Problems Encountered by the Students that Led to Remediation Program

Lack of self-confidence. This theme showed fear and hesitation in participating in classroom activities such as expressing their ideas and insights which indicated a doubt in their ability to answer correctly. This hinders engagement and academic growth in the performance of learners. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that they are afraid to talk or recite.

“Kinakabahan po ako kapag nagpaparecite si Ma’am sa harap, baka po kasi mali yung mga isasagot ko, and dun lang po ako nahihirapan. Pero nakaya ko naman po kasi magaling po si Ma’am magturo.” – Student 1

“Okay naman po siya kaso natatakot lang talaga ako na mag recite sa harapan ni Mam” – Student 3

Lack of focus. This theme that had emerged from the given data highlighted the students’ difficulty in managing their focus on specific tasks which were driven by external factors which lead to low academic performance. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that they are having difficulty with the subject due to external factors such as noise and other distractions.

“About sa determine the age of rock nahirapan ako dahil hindi ko masyado na gets ang lesson at mabilis ako madistract.” – Student 8

“Nahirapan ako sa Central Dogma of Molecular Biology kasi hindi ko gaanong maintindihan ang lesson kasi hindi ako gaanong nakinig at don ako lalong nahirapan kasi di ako makafocus kasi maingay sa likod.” – Student 9

Complex terminologies. This theme displayed struggle of students in understanding scientific concepts due to unfamiliar words, too technical terms, and the too many numbers of words which hinder the students’ understanding of the subject matter or the given concept. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that they are having a hard time understanding the lesson due to its terminologies.

“I don’t see it as difficult. Our teacher is good at teaching. I am just confused with the types of rocks because it’s too many terms.” – Student 2

“The difficulty that I encountered are the terminologies, the people, and the different discoveries.”

– Student 12

“I felt difficulty in understanding the topic that wasn’t familiar to me as well as in answering questions.” – Student 13

Absenteeism. This theme showed students frequent absences in class which resulted in low academic performance due to non-submission of class activities and inability to cope up with the subject matter. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that they were chosen for remediation program due to frequent absences.

“For me, there’s no difficulties that I encountered in learning Earth and Life to Mrs. Tenorio. She teaches lessons smoothly, so I don’t see any difficulties. I am at remediation because sometimes I’m absent and that’s why I can’t passed an activities.” – Student 7

“Sa totoo lang po madali lang po sya kaso minsan may nahihirapan po pero okay lang po yung lesson. Kapag absent ako ng araw na may discuss ang aking guro kaya nahuli at hindi ko maintindihan yung kanyang lesson pero now po naiintindihan ko na po lahat ng lesson ni ma’am.”
– Student 15

2. Students’ Experiences in Earth and Life Science Remediation Program

Enhanced learning. This theme manifested situations where students were able to strengthen their previous learning with another learning drawn from the remediation program. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that they gained more knowledge and idea because of the remediation program.

“Ang aking learning experiences sa remediation ay mas nakatanggap ako ng maraming kaalaman tungkol sa mga lessons na minsan na naming natalakay. Nagkaroon ako ng dagdag kaalaman.” – Student 5

“Sa pag take ko ng remediation mas lalong nadagdagan yung knowledge ko, mas nagkaroon pa ng idea.” – Student 1

Self-improvement. This theme demonstrated personal development and growth among the students as they undergone the remediation program. This highlighted their ability to manage time effectively, observe keenly, listen attentively, and be a responsible student. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that they improved their selves as they undergone the remediation program.

“Natutunan ko sa remediation ko sa subject na ELS ay ang kung paano mag observe at tumingin sa tinuturo para mas maintindihan ka.” – Student 4

“I learned that time management is a must. Also, I learned how to analyze, evaluate in any situations.” – Student 6

“I learned in the remediation is to advance study para kapag recitation or mga quizzes ay advance ako at maging responsible sa pag-aaral.” – Student 12

“Natutunan ko palaging mag aral at makinig sa mga tinuturo at mayroon din akong natutunan sa mga paligid at mga tungkol sa Earth.” – Student 14

Improved understanding. This theme displayed students’ increased understanding of scientific concepts which led to clarification of concepts and students’ ability to grasp easily the lesson. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that they were able to understand well and explain scientific concepts because of the remediation program.

“Masaya kasi parang na expand yung kaalaman namin sa ELS and big help talaga kasi mas naiintindihan ko na yung lesson na hindi ko naintindihan before.” – Student 3

“Ang learning experience ko sa remedial ay yung pinapaliwanag ang isang lesson at yun ang magandang karanasan ko sa remediation kasi mas madali ko itong maintindihan at naipaliwanag ko ito ng maayos.” – Student 9

“Dahil po dito ang mga late discuss ko is lalo po sya naintindihan salamat po dahil dito mas lalo pa magkakaroon ng knowledge.” – Student 15

3. Students’ Perceived Effectiveness in the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program

Improved learning. This theme reflected a positive impact on the students’ learning after the remediation program. It gave emphasis on how the remediation program provided better learning outcomes through guided practice and active participation. This theme was supported by learners who claimed that the remediation program helped them to improve and understand more scientific concepts and easily get answers on certain questions as well as improved their academic grades.

“Yes! Effective sya at nakakatulong sa mga students na mababa ang mga scores sa activities. It help to other people to improve or to learn our students on how it is, how do you really know this, at kung paano mas lalong nakukuha ng mga students ang sagot.” – Student 4

“Tumaas ang aking grade at nakatulong ito sakin para mas ma gets ang lesson ng mabuti” – Student 8

“Epektibo ang remedial kasi mas gagaling ka sa lesson na napag-iwanan mo at mas epektibo ito kasi mapapadali kana sa pag intindi ng lesson at maka sagot ka na ng maayos.” – Student 9

“Naging effective ang pag take ko sa remediation kasi nadagdagan yung sa grades ko at pumasa ako. At mas naiintindihan ko yung mga hindi ko alam na term.” – Student 13

Improved self-confidence. This theme that emerged from the given data set showed improvement in the ability of the students to participate actively in class especially in recitation. This highlighted how the remediation program helped the learners to feel confident, safe, and encouraged in every class activity. This is supported by the learners who claim that remediation helped them become participative in class.

“Subrang laki ng naitulong niya sa akin, katulad ng sinabi ko po kanina, kasi 119on guna di ako nagtataas ng kamay kasi feeling ko mali masasagot ko, pero hindi natutunan ko na, na di lahat ng bagay, kailangan nating unahin ang kahihyan, kaya simula po nun, tumataas na po ako ng kamay.” – Student 1

Learning growth. This theme demonstrated a continuous learning development among the students after they participated in the remediation program. It reflected how the students gradually improve their learning through the exposure to different learning activities. This is supported by the learners who claim that the remediation helped them learn new knowledge, skills, and understanding.

“Honestly, it’s really effective kasi sa mga sinabi ko nga na nakakatulong at na e-expand yung kaalaman namin sa isang lesson na hindi namin naintindihan.” – Student 3

“Ang aking pananaw ay mas nagging epektibo ang pag-aaral ng mga estudyante kung mayroong remediation dahil mas napapalawak pa ang kaalaman ng mga estudyante sa mga talakayin na hindi masyadong nauunawaan.” – Student 5

“For me, the effectiveness of the remediation is very clear and visible. Especially to me, I’ve learned new things because of this.” – Student 6

Knowledge reinforcement. This theme reflected how the remediation program helped the students recall and strengthen previously learned concepts. It gave emphasis how the repetition and review provided an impact in the knowledge retention among the students. This is supported by the claim of the learners that the remediation program helped them remember previous lessons and helped them in assessments.

“Nakatulong sa akin ang remediation dahil yung mga lesson na nakalimutan ko ay mas lalo kong naintindiahn at naalala”. – Student 11

“May mas natutunan pa ako tungkol sa earth and mayroon akong naalala nung remediation na nasa exam.” – Student 14

4. Students’ Suggestions for the Improvement of the Design and Implementation of Earth and Life Science Remediation Program

Learning satisfaction. This theme reflected contentment and fulfillment of the students in the remediation program with regards to their learning experience. This highlighted a positive towards learning. This is supported by the students who claim that they feel satisfied after the remediation program as well as stating that there is no need for it to be changed.

“Wala naman po. Well actually maganda ang implementation ng Earth and Life Science sa pagreredial, Maganda ang pagtuturo at maayos napaliwanag, patuloy na mag improve ang remediation lalo na sa mga students.” – Student 4

“This is very effective and positive. I do not see any problem with this. No need to improve.” – Student 6

“I don’t think there will be more improving because for me what Ma’am Tenorio is already doing is enough for students to catch up the lessons and activities because that what I felt when I’m in the remediation. It’s enough and perfect on the way it is if the students consider it.” – Student 7

Recitation. This theme showed that students suggested to have activities that focuses more on oral recitation which will serve as an avenue to develop their communication skills, verbal engagement, and self-confidence to better achieve learning outcomes. This is supported by the claim of the students that recitation must be given often during remediation to further assess learning.

“Yung nagpapagawa po ng activity si Ma’am, di lang po dapat ipapasa ng ganun lang dapat kailangan muna ipaliwanag, kasi yung ibang sagot di nila alam mga sinasagot nila basta sagot lang, kaya po daming mababang mga score, kailangan pong mag improve ng mga students na mag recite.” – Student 1

“Magparecite din para alam nila yung sinasagutan nila cuz we all know na puro AI na lang, kahit ako need ko din ang AI minsan pero much better na e pa recite para maintindihan ng buo.” – Student 3

“Magkaroon lang siguro ng more activity tsaka more recitation after magsagot.” – Student 13

Interactive activities. This theme reflected that students suggested to have interactive activities and engaging activities for the students to be more motivated and interested to learn. It showed how interactive activities increased motivation and engagement among the students and provided a meaningful learning

experience. It is supported by the claim of the learners that educational games could be helpful to achieve meaningful learning outcomes.

“Suggest ko na hindi dapat mawala and remediation dahil nakakatulong ito at during sa remediation i-suggest kulang na magpalaro na related sa subject para mas maintindihan ang lesson at during sa pag recall ng topic, mamimigay ng chips para mas ganado ang mga estudyante mag recite.” – Student 10

“I suggest na may pa games para kahit papano ay maging interested ang mga students sa lesson o pag-aaral.” – Student 11

“Magkaroon ng quiz bee at kaunting palaro para sa mga remediation” – Student 14

Remediation schedules. This theme that emerged from the given data set highlighted the suggestion of the learners that remediation schedules should be longer. It showed that remediation schedules influenced students’ ability to effectively understand the lesson. It is supported by the claim of the students that remediation schedule should be longer or at least twice a week to for the students to better grasp the concept.

“Ang masusuggest ko is magpatuloy at para maimprove is mag twice a week mag remediation.” – Student 3

“Para po sa akin ang mga batang katulad ko na slow learner or mahina makaintindi is kailangan po ito para maintindihan ang isang bagay need po siguro dito ng more activities at mahabang oras para dito” – Student 15

Plans for Dissemination and Advocacy

Research Topic	Objectives	Target Audience	Channels	Key Messages	Timeline	Evaluation Process
Exploring Students’ Perspective in Earth and Life Science Remediation Program: A Phenomenology	<p>Determine the students’ difficulties and experiences, in the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program</p> <p>Determine the student’s suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the design and implementation of remediation program</p> <p>Develop work action plan</p>	students	<p>remediation schedules</p> <p>Work Action Plan</p>	This study emphasizes the lived experiences of the students who participated in the Earth and Life Science Remediation Program disclosing their academic and personal growth.	<p>Consolidation of Assessment Scores (Month 1)</p> <p>Determination of Remediation Program Participant based on Assessment Scores (Month 1)</p> <p>Conduct of Remediation Program in Earth and Life Science (Month 2)</p> <p>Development and Validation of Questionnaire (Month 3)</p>	<p>quick surveys to assess the relevance of the learning activities in remediation program</p> <p>monitoring of the remediation program</p>

	based on the suggestions and recommendations of the students for the improvement of the design and implementation of remediation program				Administration of the Validated Questionnaire to the Target Participants (Month 4)	
					Analysis and Interpretation of Data (Month 5)	
					Development of Conclusion and Recommendation (Month 5)	

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